

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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1 Executive summary

Despite their small size, aerosols strongly influence Earth's climate. They scatter and absorb radiation but also modify the properties of clouds as cloud droplets form on aerosol particles.^{4,5} New climate simulations at the kilometer-scale allow us to examine long-standing questions related to these interactions such as the potential invigoration of convective clouds or the enhancement of cloud amount. To perform kilometer-scale simulations with interactive aerosols, we developed the simple aerosol module HAM-lite and linked it to the climate model ICON-Sapphire. HAM-lite is based on and fully traceable to the complex aerosol module HAM.^{25,30} Like in HAM, aerosols are represented as an ensemble of log-normal modes. Unlike in HAM, aerosol microphysics is discarded and aerosol sizes and compositions are prescribed. With that, we only need prognostic tracers for aerosol concentrations and in turn reduce the computational burden significantly.

2 Conclusion & Results

To evaluate the aerosol module, we performed a global simulation with ICON-Sapphire coupled to HAM-lite at a resolution of five kilometers and over a period of 40 days. Apart from prescribing the sea surface temperature and sea ice instead of simulating an interactive ocean, the simulation was set up as described in the publication of Hohenegger *et al.*¹⁵ Aerosols were represented by four modes composed of dust, sea salt, organic carbon, black carbon, and sulfate. We performed the simulation on the Levante cluster of the German Climate Computing Center.⁶ The computational throughput was 40 simulated days per day on 400 nodes.

The simulation captures key elements of the global aerosol cycle, which are only partially represented in coarse-scale simulations. The figures in section 4.2.2 show the transport of dust aerosols across the Atlantic and the interplay of sea salt aerosols with a cyclone in the Pacific. Over the Sahara, we observe a dust storm driven by a cold pool front. Across the Atlantic, we observe the doldrums, a large-scale band of low surface winds resulting in low levels of sea salt aerosols. Further simulations over longer periods of up to a year are currently being performed to refine the aerosol module and to extend the statistical analysis.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
01	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes

O2

To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:

(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	yes
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stocktake.	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	no
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP4	Relevance in this deliverable?
To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5). (O1)	yes
To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures. (O1)	yes
To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO ₂ and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase. (O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Aerosols originate from natural processes, like wind-driven emissions of dust or sea spray, but also from human activities, like biomass burning or fuel combustion. Aerosols scatter and absorb radiation, referred to as aerosol-radiation interactions, but also modify the formation and properties of clouds, referred to as aerosol-cloud interactions. How these interactions influence the climate is still uncertain, despite decades of research.^{4,5} With new climate simulations at kilometer resolutions, we are now able to test long-standing hypotheses related to these interactions such as the potential invigoration of convective clouds or the enhancement of cloud amount and optical thickness by aerosols.^{15,29}

4.1 Implementation

To examine these processes with the climate model ICON-Sapphire, we developed the one-moment aerosol module HAM-lite, based on and fully traceable to the two-moment module HAM.^{25,30} The size distribution of aerosols is represented by an ensemble of log-normal modes. The microphysical interactions of aerosols are discarded such that the mean radius and standard deviation of a mode are prescribed. The selection of modes is flexible. A mode can be within the Aitken, accumulation, or coarse range, i.e., the mean radius can range from $0.005 \mu\text{m}$ to above $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. And a mode can be composed of internal mixtures of dust, sea salt, black carbon, organic carbon, or sulfate, i.e., all particles within a mode consist of the same mixture of species.²⁴ The calculation of aerosol properties, which govern aerosol processes like sedimentation or wet deposition, remains fully consistent with HAM. The modes of HAM-lite interact with the processes of ICON-Sapphire, i.e., aerosols are transported as tracers in its dynamical core and are coupled to its parameterization schemes.^{15,34}

4.1.1 Aerosol modes

Previous studies showed that the size distribution of aerosols can be represented as a superposition of log-normal modes

$$N(\ln r) = \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{N_j}{\sqrt{2\pi \ln \sigma_j}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln r - \ln \bar{r}_j)^2}{2 \ln^2 \sigma_j}\right),$$

in which J is the number of modes.³⁰ Each mode is defined by three moments, i.e., the particle number N_j , mean (or dry) radius \bar{r}_j , and standard deviation σ_j . In the two-moment scheme HAM, the particle number and mean radius are variable whereas the standard deviation is prescribed. A particle in a mode j is composed of different species k with masses M_j^k , which vary due to microphysical processes such as coagulation or condensation. In the modal structure of HAM, there are four hydrophilic and three hydrophobic modes in the nucleation, Aitken, accumulation, and coarse range, as shown in table 3. The particles are composed of internal mixtures of five species, i.e., dust, sea salt, sulfate, organic carbon, and black carbon. In a climate simulation, the particle numbers and mass fractions are represented as prognostic tracers.²⁵

The transport of prognostic tracers requires significant computational resources such that the two-moment scheme HAM can only be used in simulations at resolutions on the order of 100 kilometers.

Table 3: Complex aerosol module HAM.³⁰

Mode (μm)	Soluble	Insoluble
Nucleation ($\bar{r} \leq 0.005$)	N_1, M_1^{su}	
Aitken ($0.005 < \bar{r} \leq 0.05$)	$N_2, M_2^{\text{su}}, M_2^{\text{bc}}, M_2^{\text{oc}}$	$N_5, M_5^{\text{bc}}, M_5^{\text{oc}}$
Accumulation ($0.05 < \bar{r} \leq 0.5$)	$N_3, M_3^{\text{su}}, M_3^{\text{bc}}, M_3^{\text{oc}}, M_3^{\text{ss}}, M_3^{\text{du}}$	N_6, M_6^{du}
Coarse ($0.5 < \bar{r}$)	$N_4, M_4^{\text{su}}, M_4^{\text{bc}}, M_4^{\text{oc}}, M_4^{\text{ss}}, M_4^{\text{du}}$	N_7, M_7^{du}

In order to make simulations at resolutions on the order of one kilometer possible, we reduce the physical complexity of HAM to the one-moment scheme HAM-lite. First, we discard microphysical processes and prescribe the mean radius and particle composition such that we only need prognostic tracers for the particle numbers. Second, we discard the hydrophobic and nucleation modes such that we can further reduce the number of prognostic tracers to about three to five. In HAM-lite, a particle in a mode j is composed of different species k with constant volume fractions α_j^k . The properties of a particle are computed as volume-weighted averages over the properties of the individual species. The density ρ_j and hygroscopicity parameter κ_j of a particle are therefore

$$\rho_j = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_j^k \rho^k \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_j = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_j^k \kappa^k,$$

in which ρ^k and κ^k are the density and hygroscopicity of the species k . Based on the dry radius and hygroscopicity, we can tabulate the wet radius of a particle as a function of the air temperature T and relative humidity RH such that

$$r_{w,j}(T, RH) = f_g(T, RH, \bar{r}_j, \kappa_j) \bar{r}_j,$$

in which f_g is the hygroscopic growth factor from Petters and Kreidenweis.²¹ Since the composition and size of a mode are prescribed, we can compute the particle properties and tabulate the wet radius once at the initialization stage. In contrast to HAM, the modal structure of HAM-lite is flexible. Table 4 shows an example with four hydrophilic modes in the Aitken, accumulation, and coarse range.

Table 4: Simplified aerosol module HAM-lite.

Mode (μm)	Soluble	Insoluble
Nucleation ($\bar{r} \leq 0.005$)		
Aitken ($0.005 < \bar{r} \leq 0.05$)	N_1	
Accumulation ($0.05 < \bar{r} \leq 0.5$)	N_2	
Coarse ($0.5 < \bar{r}$)	N_3, N_4	

4.1.2 Aerosol processes

The prognostic tracers representing aerosols are transported through the atmosphere and influenced by various processes such as emission, wet deposition, dry deposition, and sedimentation. Figure 1

shows the prognostic variables and their spatial discretization in the climate model ICON-Sapphire.²³ The prognostic variables are the virtual temperature θ_v , the air density ρ_a , the horizontal and vertical velocities v_n and w , and the tracers q_i , which represent either specific masses in the cloud scheme or particle numbers in the aerosol scheme. Horizontally, the sphere is discretized with an icosahedral grid. Vertically, the column is divided into levels based on terrain-following coordinates.^{15,35}

Figure 1: Spatial discretization and prognostic variables: icosahedral grid with equilateral triangles (left) and vertical column with full and half levels (right).¹⁰ Prognostic tracers that belong to the cloud or aerosol scheme are highlighted in red.

Due to the grid spacing on the order of a kilometer, smaller-scale processes cannot be resolved and have to be parameterized. These parameterized processes impose tendencies on the prognostic variables. There are three parameterization schemes for cloud microphysics, radiation, and turbulence as shown in figure 2. Cloud microphysics are parameterized with the one-moment scheme of Baldauf *et al.*³ The scheme computes the specific masses of six water classes, i.e., water vapor, cloud water, cloud ice, rain, snow, and graupel. Radiation is parameterized with the radiative transfer scheme from Pincus *et al.*²² The scheme computes radiative properties and fluxes over 14 shortwave bands and 16 longwave bands. Turbulence is parameterized with the Smagorinsky scheme even though turbulent eddies are only partially resolved at the kilometer scale.⁷ Note that the representation of sub-grid scale turbulence is examined in the related work package 4.4. Due to its computational complexity, the radiation scheme is called less frequently than the cloud microphysics and turbulence schemes.^{13,15}

The aerosol module interacts with these schemes, e.g., for the formation of cloud droplets from aerosol particles serving as cloud condensation nuclei or the emission of aerosol particles at the surface. Figure 2 shows how the parameterization schemes of ICON-Sapphire and HAM-lite are coupled to each other.²⁵ Wet deposition is linked to the cloud microphysics scheme, radiative properties of aerosols are factored into the radiation scheme, and dry deposition and emission are linked to the turbulence and land schemes. Sedimentation is called separately at the end of the cycle. In the next paragraphs, we briefly discuss the schemes of HAM-lite.

Figure 2: Time stepping and atmospheric processes: dynamical core and tracer transport (black), parameterized processes (blue), and land scheme (green). Processes of the climate model are listed in black, whereas processes of the aerosol module are listed in red.¹⁵

Emission: The emission fluxes are computed interactively or prescribed from emission data sets. Sea salt emissions are computed with a scheme from Long *et al.*¹⁹ based on the 10 m wind speed and sea surface temperature. Dust emissions are computed with a scheme from Tegen *et al.*³³ based on the 10 m wind speed, soil humidity, and snow cover. The emissions of sulfate, organic carbon, and black carbon are taken from the AeroCom-II ACCMIP database.¹² It provides monthly averages of emissions from anthropogenic sources and biomass burning.²⁵ Note that emission fluxes are computed for individual species, whereas aerosol particles are internal mixtures of different species. The emission flux of a species is therefore converted into an emission flux of a particle if the particle contains that species. In future simulations, the emission fluxes will be used to define the composition of a particle.

Radiation: The radiative properties of aerosols are evaluated according to Mie theory. Based on the Mie size parameter $X_j = 2\pi r_{w,j}/\lambda$ and refractive index $n_j = n_{\text{real},j} + i n_{\text{imag},j}$, the radiative properties are extracted from look-up tables. Similar to the other particle properties, the real and imaginary parts of the refractive index are computed as volume-weighted averages over the individual species including water, such that

$$n_{\text{real},j} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K V_j^k n_{\text{real}}^k + V_j^{\text{wa}} n_{\text{real}}^{\text{wa}}}{\sum_{k=1}^K V_j^k + V_j^{\text{wa}}} \quad \text{and} \quad n_{\text{imag},j} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K V_j^k n_{\text{imag}}^k + V_j^{\text{wa}} n_{\text{imag}}^{\text{wa}}}{\sum_{k=1}^K V_j^k + V_j^{\text{wa}}},$$

in which the water content V^{wa} is computed based on the difference between the wet and dry radius. The aerosol optical depth is diagnosed for longwave and shortwave bands, whereas the single scattering albedo and asymmetry factor are diagnosed only for shortwave bands.³⁰

Wet deposition: The wet deposition flux is computed for all grid cells within a cloud as

$$F_{\text{wd},j} = N_j f_{\text{ac},j} e_{\text{pr}},$$

in which $f_{ac,j}$ is the fraction of activation and e_{pr} is the precipitation efficiency.¹⁸ The fraction of activation is calculated from the dry radius and critical radius according to Köhler theory.^{1,2} The precipitation efficiency is the ratio of the surface precipitation of rain to the column-integrated cloud water.¹⁸ The number of activated particles is factored into the autoconversion rate of the cloud microphysics scheme and into the cloud properties of the radiation scheme.^{13,22,26}

Dry deposition: The dry deposition surface flux is computed as

$$F_{dd,j} = N_{sr,j} v_{dd,j},$$

in which $N_{sr,j}$ is the particle concentration in the surface level and $v_{dd,j}$ is the dry deposition velocity. The dry deposition flux is subtracted from the emission surface flux such that a net surface flux is returned as the lower boundary condition to the turbulence scheme. The dry deposition velocity is computed with a serial resistance scheme of Ganzeveld *et al.*^{8,9} based on the wet radius, particle density, surface wind speed, and various surface properties.³⁰

Sedimentation: The sedimentation flux is computed throughout the column as

$$F_{sd,j} = N_j \frac{v_{sd,j}}{\Delta z},$$

in which $v_{sd,j}$ is the sedimentation velocity and Δz is the distance between two levels. The sedimentation velocity is computed according to Stokes theory based on the wet radius, particle density, air viscosity, and gravitational acceleration. It includes a correction factor to account for non-continuum effects.²⁷ And it is limited to $\Delta z / \Delta t_{A,L}$ to ensure numerical stability, in which $\Delta t_{A,L}$ is the time step of the atmosphere and land as shown in figure 2.³⁰

4.2 Evaluation

To evaluate the aerosol module, we performed a simulation with ICON-Sapphire and HAM-lite at a resolution of about five kilometers and over a period of 40 days. In order to reduce the computational burden, we prescribed the sea surface temperature and sea ice. The simulation was performed on the Levante cluster of the German Climate Computing Center and analyzed at the Cycle 3 Hackathon in May 2023.⁶ The initial results shown below in section 4.2.2 are promising. In the next months, the evaluation will be extended. We are currently performing further simulations over longer periods of up to a year. And we are planning to evaluate our simulations against satellite observations and comparable simulations at coarser resolutions.²⁸

4.2.1 Simulation setup

Apart from the prescribed ocean boundary conditions, the simulation was set up as described in the recent publication of Hohenegger *et al.*¹⁵ The atmosphere is represented as described in section 4.1.2, the land is represented with the dynamic vegetation model JSBACH,¹¹ and the boundary conditions of the ocean are taken from the AMIP II database.³² Horizontally, the atmosphere and land are discretized with the R2B9 grid which corresponds to a grid spacing of about five kilometers. Vertically, the atmosphere is divided into 90 levels with a thickness of 25 – 400 m, and the land is

divided into five levels with a thickness of 0.065 – 5700 m. The time step of the atmosphere and land is $\Delta t_{A,L} = 40$ s and the time step of the radiation is $\Delta t_{\text{rad}} = 12$ min. The initial conditions of the atmosphere and land are derived from the ERA5 reanalysis of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts.¹⁴

Aerosols are represented by four modes as shown in table 5. There are two pure modes, one of dust and one of sea salt, and two internally mixed modes, both of organic carbon, black carbon, and sulfate. The volume fractions of the three species are $\alpha_3^{\text{bc}} = 0.5$, $\alpha_3^{\text{oc}} = 0.25$, and $\alpha_3^{\text{su}} = 0.25$ in the smaller mode and $\alpha_4^{\text{su}} = 0.5$, $\alpha_4^{\text{bc}} = 0.25$, and $\alpha_4^{\text{oc}} = 0.25$ in the large mode. Note that these volume fractions were chosen by us without prior analysis. The mean radii of the four modes were taken from the MACv2 aerosol climatology of Kinne¹⁶ and the densities and hygroscopicities of the five species were taken from Stier *et al.*³⁰ and Takemura *et al.*³¹ The emissions of black carbon, organic carbon, and sulfate are based on the RCP4.5 scenario. The simulation starts on 22 August 2020 and runs over 40 days until 1 October 2020. The first 10 days are discarded as spin-up and not included in the analysis.¹³ In future simulations, the selection of modes will be refined, for example, the volume fractions of organic carbon, black carbon, and sulfate will be derived from their emission fluxes.

Table 5: Aerosol modes.

Mode	Radius (μm)	Density (kg/m^3)	Hygroscopicity
du	0.93	2.65	0.140
ss	0.75	2.16	1.160
bc (oc, su)	0.03	1.96	0.163
su (bc, oc)	0.08	1.92	0.290

4.2.2 Simulation results

To start with, we examine the aerosol burdens, i.e., the column-integrated aerosol masses, on 1 October 2020. Figure 3 shows the instantaneous burdens of all four modes. The corresponding monthly averages are shown in table 6 (left). And figure 4 shows the burden of sea salt together with the column-integrated cloud water and ice and surface precipitation. The figures highlight various processes, for example, the transport of dust particles across the Atlantic or the washout of sea salt particles by rain bands. Note that the background image in figures 3 to 6 is taken from NASA Visible Earth.²⁰ To show the different fields together with the background image in one figure, the color bars are completely transparent at the minimum values.

Second, we examine the fluxes of sea salt aerosols. Figure 5 (a) shows zonal averages of the sea salt burden and fluxes due to emission, wet deposition, dry deposition, and sedimentation. The corresponding monthly averages are shown in table 6 (right). The positive and negative fluxes roughly balance out. The zonal averages of the emission and wet deposition flux show a distinct peak at a latitude of about 20 degrees. That peak is linked to a cyclone in the Pacific as captured in figures 5 (b) and (c). To highlight the magnitude of the cyclone, the color bars in these figures extend over a three times wider range than in figure 4. This illustrates the impact of local events on global statistics in kilometer-scale simulations.

Third, we examine the vertical distribution of aerosols throughout the atmospheric column. Figures 6 (b) and (c) show aerosol concentrations averaged over the lowest 20 levels, corresponding to a height of about 0.24 km to 4.19 km, and over 20 intermediate levels, corresponding to a height of about 4.19 km to 12.02 km. The corresponding vertical profiles are shown in figure 6 (a). The vertical distributions of the four modes differ clearly. Sea salt particles are removed by dry and wet deposition at low levels due to their large radius and hygroscopicity, whereas black carbon particles are lifted up to high levels due to their small radius and hygroscopicity. This illustrates the impact of aerosol properties on processes like vertical transport.

Lastly, we take a closer look at the interaction of wind speed with dust and sea salt aerosols in the surface level. Figure 7 shows how the surface concentrations of these particles are driven by the surface wind speed. Over the Sahara, we see high dust concentrations over the Bodélé depression in Chad and a dust storm in Mauritania moving towards the coast. And over the Atlantic, we see the doldrums with low surface wind speeds and few sea salt aerosols.¹⁷

Table 6: Aerosol burdens (left) and sea salt fluxes (right) averaged over space and time from 1 to 30 September.

Mode	Burden (mg/m ²)	Process	Flux (mg/m ² /s)
du	105.5	Emission	$3.265 \cdot 10^{-5}$
ss	0.9804	Wet deposition	$-2.093 \cdot 10^{-5}$
bc (oc, su)	0.2372	Dry deposition	$-1.382 \cdot 10^{-5}$
su (bc, oc)	5.855	Sedimentation	$-5.592 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Figure 3: Aerosol burdens on 1 October.

Figure 4: Sea salt burden, cloud water and ice, and precipitation on 1 October.

Figure 5: Atmospheric processes of sea salt: zonal averages of sea salt burden (mg/m^2) and fluxes ($\text{mg/m}^2/\text{s}$) averaged over 1 to 30 September (a) and maps of sea salt burden together with cloud water and ice and precipitation on 18 September [(b) and (c)].²⁰

Figure 6: Vertical distribution of aerosol modes: vertical profiles of aerosol concentrations averaged over 1 to 30 September (a) and maps of aerosol concentrations on 21 September averaged over low levels 70 to 90 (b) and intermediate level 50 to 70 (c).²⁰

Figure 7: Wind speed [(a) and (b)] and mass concentrations of dust (c) and sea salt (d) in the lowest level at a height of approximately 240 m on 21 September.

5 References (Bibliography)

- [1] Hayder Abdul-Razzak and Steven J. Ghan. A parameterization of aerosol activation: 2. Multiple aerosol types. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 105(D5):6837–6844, 2000.
- [2] Hayder Abdul-Razzak, Steven J. Ghan, and Carlos Rivera-Carpio. A parameterization of aerosol activation: 1. Single aerosol type. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 103(D6):6123–6131, 1998.
- [3] Michael Baldauf, Axel Seifert, Jochen Förstner, Detlev Majewski, Matthias Raschendorfer, and Thorsten Reinhardt. Operational Convective-Scale Numerical Weather Prediction with the COSMO Model: Description and Sensitivities. *Monthly Weather Review*, 139(12):3887 – 3905, 2011.
- [4] Frida A.-M. Bender. Aerosol Forcing: Still Uncertain, Still Relevant. *AGU Advances*, 1(3):e2019AV000128, 2020.
- [5] O. Boucher, D. Randall, P. Artaxo, C. Bretherton, G. Feingold, P. Forster, V.-M. Kerminen, Y. Kondo, H. Liao, U. Lohmann, P. Rasch, S.K. Satheesh, S. Sherwood, B. Stevens, and X.Y. Zhang. Clouds and Aerosols. In T.F. Stocker, D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex, and P.M. Midgley, editors, *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, 2013.

- [6] German Climate Computing Center. Levante. https://www.dkrz.de/en/systems/hpc/hlre-4-levante?set_language=en, 2023.
- [7] Anurag Dipankar, Bjorn Stevens, Rieke Heinze, Christopher Moseley, Günther Zängl, Marco Giorgetta, and Slavko Brdar. Large eddy simulation using the general circulation model ICON. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 7(3):963–986, 2015.
- [8] Laurens Ganzeveld and Jos Lelieveld. Dry deposition parameterization in a chemistry general circulation model and its influence on the distribution of reactive trace gases. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 100(D10):20999–21012, 1995.
- [9] Laurens Ganzeveld, Jos Lelieveld, and Geert-Jan Roelofs. A dry deposition parameterization for sulfur oxides in a chemistry and general circulation model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 103(D5):5679–5694, 1998.
- [10] M. A. Giorgetta, R. Brokopf, T. Crueger, M. Esch, S. Fiedler, J. Helmert, C. Hohenegger, L. Kornblueh, M. Köhler, E. Manzini, T. Mauritsen, C. Nam, T. Raddatz, S. Rast, D. Reinert, M. Sakradzija, H. Schmidt, R. Schneck, R. Schnur, L. Silvers, H. Wan, G. Zängl, and B. Stevens. Icon-a, the atmosphere component of the icon earth system model: I. model description. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 10(7):1613–1637, 2018.
- [11] D. Goll, S. Hagemann, M. Heidkamp, J.E.M.S. Nabel, T. Raddatz, E. Roeckner, R. Schnur, and S. Wilkenskjaeld. JSACH 3 - The land component of the MPI Earth System Model: Documentation of version 3.2. Technical Report 240, Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie, 2021.
- [12] A. Heil, M. Schultz, and C. Granier. AeroCom II emission data. <https://aerocom-classic.met.no/DATA/download/emissions/AEROCOM-II-ACCMIP/>, 2022.
- [13] R. J. Herbert, A. I. L. Williams, P. Weiss, D. Watson-Parris, E. Dingley, D. Klocke, and P. Stier. Isolating aerosol-climate interactions in global storm-resolving simulations. *[Manuscript in preparation]*, 2023.
- [14] Hans Hersbach, Bill Bell, Paul Berrisford, Shoji Hirahara, András Horányi, Joaquín Muñoz-Sabater, Julien Nicolas, Carole Peubey, Raluca Radu, Dinand Schepers, Adrian Simmons, Cornel Soci, Saleh Abdalla, Xavier Abellan, Gianpaolo Balsamo, Peter Bechtold, Gionata Biavati, Jean Bidlot, Massimo Bonavita, Giovanna De Chiara, Per Dahlgren, Dick Dee, Michail Diamantakis, Rossana Dragani, Johannes Flemming, Richard Forbes, Manuel Fuentes, Alan Geer, Leo Haimberger, Sean Healy, Robin J. Hogan, Elías Hólm, Marta Janisková, Sarah Keeley, Patrick Laloyaux, Philippe Lopez, Cristina Lupu, Gabor Radnoti, Patricia de Rosnay, Iryna Rozum, Freja Vamborg, Sebastien Villaume, and Jean-Noël Thépaut. The era5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146(730):1999–2049, 2020.
- [15] C. Hohenegger, P. Korn, L. Linardakis, R. Redler, R. Schnur, P. Adamidis, J. Bao, S. Bastin, M. Behraves, M. Bergemann, J. Biercamp, H. Bockelmann, R. Brokopf, N. Brüggemann, L. Casaroli, F. Chegini, G. Datseris, M. Esch, G. George, M. Giorgetta, O. Gutjahr, H. Haak, M. Hanke, T. Ilyina, T. Jahns, J. Jungclaus, M. Kern, D. Klocke, L. Kluft, T. Kölling, L. Kornblueh, S. Kosukhin, C. Kroll, J. Lee, T. Mauritsen, C. Mehlmann, T. Mieslinger, A. K. Naumann, L. Paccini, A. Peinado, D. S. Praturi, D. Putrasahan, S. Rast, T. Riddick, N. Roeber, H. Schmidt, U. Schulzweida, F. Schütte, H. Segura, R. Shevchenko, V. Singh, M. Specht, C. C.

- Stephan, J.-S. von Storch, R. Vogel, C. Wengel, M. Winkler, F. Ziemer, J. Marotzke, and B. Stevens. ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 16(2):779–811, 2023.
- [16] S. Kinne. The MACv2 aerosol climatology. *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*, 71(1):1–21, 2019.
- [17] Daniel Klocke, Matthias Brueck, Cathy Hohenegger, and Bjorn Stevens. Rediscovery of the doldrums in storm-resolving simulations over the tropical Atlantic. *Nature Geoscience*, 10:891–896, 2017.
- [18] Ryan L. Li, Joshua H. P. Studholme, Alexey V. Fedorov, and Trude Storelvmo. Precipitation efficiency constraint on climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(7):642–648, 2022.
- [19] M. S. Long, W. C. Keene, D. J. Kieber, D. J. Erickson, and H. Maring. A sea-state based source function for size- and composition-resolved marine aerosol production. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 11(3):1203–1216, 2011.
- [20] NASA. Visible Earth. <https://visibleearth.nasa.gov/collection/1484/blue-marble>, 2023.
- [21] M. D. Petters and S. M. Kreidenweis. A single parameter representation of hygroscopic growth and cloud condensation nucleus activity. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 7(8):1961–1971, 2007.
- [22] Robert Pincus, Eli J. Mlawer, and Jennifer S. Delamere. Balancing Accuracy, Efficiency, and Flexibility in Radiation Calculations for Dynamical Models. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 11(10):3074–3089, 2019.
- [23] F. Prill, D. Reinert, D. Rieger, and G. Zängl. ICON Tutorial. <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/Documentation>, 2020.
- [24] N. Riemer, A. P. Ault, M. West, R. L. Craig, and J. H. Curtis. Aerosol mixing state: Measurements, modeling, and impacts. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 57(2):187–249, 2019.
- [25] M. Salzmann, S. Ferrachat, C. Tully, S. Münch, D. Watson-Parris, D. Neubauer, C. Siegenthaler-Le Drian, S. Rast, B. Heinold, T. Crueger, R. Brokopf, J. Mülmenstädt, J. Quaas, H. Wan, K. Zhang, U. Lohmann, P. Stier, and I. Tegen. The Global Atmosphere-aerosol Model ICON-AHAM2.3—Initial Model Evaluation and Effects of Radiation Balance Tuning on Aerosol Optical Thickness. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(4):e2021MS002699, 2022.
- [26] A. Seifert and K. D. Beheng. A two-moment cloud microphysics parameterization for mixed-phase clouds. Part 1: Model description. *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, 92(1):45–66, 2006.
- [27] John H. Seinfeld and Spyros N. Pandis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics: From Air Pollution to Climate Change*. Wiley, 2016.
- [28] Graeme L. Stephens, Matthew Christensen, Timothy Andrews, James Haywood, Florent F. Malavelle, Kentaroh Suzuki, Xianwen Jing, Mathew Lebsock, Jui-Lin F. Li, Hanii Takahashi,

- and Ousmane Sy. Cloud physics from space. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 145(724):2854–2875, 2019.
- [29] Bjorn Stevens, Masaki Satoh, Ludovic Auger, Joachim Biercamp, Christopher S. Bretherton, Xi Chen, Peter Düben, Falko Judt, Marat Khairoutdinov, Daniel Klocke, Chihiro Kodama, Luis Kornbluh, Shian-Jiann Lin, Philipp Neumann, William M. Putman, Niklas Röber, Ryosuke Shibuya, Benoit Vanniere, Pier Luigi Vidale, Nils Wedi, and Linjiong Zhou. DYAMOND: the Dynamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science*, 6(1):61, 2019.
- [30] P. Stier, J. Feichter, S. Kinne, S. Kloster, E. Vignati, J. Wilson, L. Ganzeveld, I. Tegen, M. Werner, Y. Balkanski, M. Schulz, O. Boucher, A. Minikin, and A. Petzold. The aerosol-climate model ECHAM5-HAM. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 5(4):1125–1156, 2005.
- [31] Toshihiko Takemura, Toru Nozawa, Seita Emori, Takashi Y. Nakajima, and Teruyuki Nakajima. Simulation of climate response to aerosol direct and indirect effects with aerosol transport-radiation model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 110(D2), 2005.
- [32] K. E. Taylor, D. Williamson, and F. Zwiers. The sea surface temperature and sea ice concentration boundary conditions for AMIP II simulations. Technical Report 60, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, 2000.
- [33] I. Tegen, D. Neubauer, S. Ferrachat, C. Siegenthaler-Le Drian, I. Bey, N. Schutgens, P. Stier, D. Watson-Parris, T. Stanelle, H. Schmidt, S. Rast, H. Kokkola, M. Schultz, S. Schroeder, N. Daskalakis, S. Barthel, B. Heinold, and U. Lohmann. The global aerosol–climate model ECHAM6.3–HAM2.3 – Part 1: Aerosol evaluation. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(4):1643–1677, 2019.
- [34] Philipp Weiss, Ross Herbert, and Philip Stier. A reduced complexity aerosol model for km-scale climate models. *EGU General Assembly*, (2082), 2023.
- [35] Günther Zängl, Daniel Reinert, Pilar Rípodas, and Michael Baldauf. The ICON (ICOsahedral Non-hydrostatic) modelling framework of DWD and MPI-M: Description of the non-hydrostatic dynamical core. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 141(687):563–579, 2015.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

7 Deliverable timeliness

Delayed by one and a half months.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This work package is closely linked to Work Package 4.3 on producing dust emissions, Work Package 4.4 on assessing sub-grid scale processes, as well as Work Package 5.1 on examining aerosol-cloud interactions and aerosol forcing. Links with the responsible working groups have been established during the Cycle 2 and 3 hackathons.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>